

“Anatomical Studies Of Heartwood Formation In Some Angiosperm Plant From Nandurbar Area Forest”

Satish V Deore

Department Of Botany, J. E.S.'s, Arts, Science and Commerce College,
Nandurbar- 425412, Maharashtra.
Email: satishvdeore@gmail.com

Abstract

Current work is deals with the anatomical studies on some selected medicinal plants including *Albizia lebbeck* (L)Willd, *Anogessus latifolia* (Roxb. Ex DC), *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss, *Diospyrus melanoxylon* Roxb, *Lagerstroemia lanceolata* Wall. ex.w, *Melia azedarach* L., *Prosopis julifera* DC, *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb and *Zizphus xylopyra* (Retz.) from Nandurbar district a part of Deccan plateau is situated in the north part of Maharashtra. Plants were selected for comparative studied between stem wood and root wood for thir heartwood and sapwood. In plant trunk wood and root wood for a better insight into the process of heartwood formation. It was find that heartwood formation with respect to different species and its parts some noticeable and conclusive result that the deciduous tree species cause radial extension of heartwood is comparatively less than evergreen species.

Key words: *Anatomincal Studeid, Angiosperm, heartwood and sapwood*

Introduction

In the present investigation comparative anatomical studies of root and stem wood. The contribution of wood to the development and sustenance's of our civilization is well known. India has several different tree species growing in its varied climatic and geographic condition unlike the European countries. There are a large tree species available however due to certain qualitative character's only a few of them are widely used for various commercial purposes (Abrams *et al.*, 1999 and Satish V. Deore 2016).

Wood is produced by a vascular cambium one layer of cell division at a time, but we know from general experience that in many woods there are large cohorts of cells produce more or less together time and these cohorts act tighter to save the tree. The living cells of the sapwood are also

the agents of heartwood formation and that also at center (Khan 2014). Heartwood forms a core with a roughly conical shape in the trunk. Once its formation initiates, the diameter and the height of the core continue to increase throughout the life of a tree (Chilar J 2000). The mechanism of heartwood formation is not clearly known in spite of various works efforts to elucidate the problem (Bisht B.S. & Kothari B. P 2001; Sarma *et al.*, 2001). Majority of the information in regards to heartwood formation revolves around conifers and knowledge on the process of heartwood formation in angiosperm is meager (Chilar J 2000).

Transformation of sapwood into heartwood is accompanied by a number of well identified biological changes in parenchyma cells (Pant D. N. and Roy P. S., 1994). The information about the biochemical process during heartwood formation is based on calorimetric procedures and is conformed mainly to the conifers tree. The present investigation will focus on the various biochemical aspects involved in heartwood formation in some angiosperm tree. To understand the changes that occur during transformation during sap wood to heartwood, some Histochemical parameter will be studied.

A living growing tree has two main domains the shoot and the roots. The root is the subterranean structure responsible for water uptake, mechanical support of the shoot and storage of biochemical. The shoot comprises the trunk or bole of the tree, the branches and leaves. Root wood has all together has different environment to that of trunk wood. Heartwood formation in root wood remains unexplored. This study leads to the better understanding of the difference on account of heartwood formation in root wood as well as stem wood.

Description of study Area: In the present study Nandurbar District has been chosen as the used for study area. Nandurbar district a part of Deccan plateau is situated in the north part of Maharashtra state between 21 N to 21.32N latitude and 73.34 E to 74.3 E longitudes (Patil & Khan 2017a). It lies in the Valley of Tapi Rivers and Satpuda mountains. The district can be divided into hilly tracts and undulating plain areas. Very small part of Narmadabasin toward the west, middle region of Satpuda Mountain, called Kandesh Satpuda, lies westward in Dhule and Jalgaon and Nandurbar.

Methodology

The wood samples are collected from the healthy tree into disc. Matched paired of clear heartwood and sapwood discus were cut into 1cm block, 10-15um thick, radial longitudinal sections were cut on wood microtome. For Histochemical localization sections were fixed into FAA(90 ml 70% ethanol: 5ml glacial acetic acid and 5 ml formaldehyde) were used. For experimental regulation different chemicals (ethylene, polyamines) were injected to the whole made in the tree trunk using an increment borer. The holes were sealed with sealing wax after the treatment

Material and Methods

Various aspect of heartwood formation has been studied in the present investigation in following manner.

Experimental Studied: For the experimental regulation were injected into the holes made in the tree trunk using as increment borer. The holes were sealed with sealing wax after the treatment. The chemical used in holes are in different concentration with intervals of decided timing (Satish V. Deore 2016).

Comparatively studies of stem and root wood: Angiosperm trees have been selected for comparative between stem wood and root wood. In plant trunk wood and root wood for a better insight into the process of heartwood formation. The logs were collected from the healthy tree of Dhanpur Forest near Taloda, Toranmal, and forest of Satpuda ranges within Nandurbar district (Photo plat 1 and 2)(Patil & Khan 2017b).

Results and Discussion

Angiospermic Species under investigation

Albizia lebbek (L)Willd.: A large deciduous tree with umbrella shape crown. Hard wood and softwood is large white or yellowish. The wood is excellent for high class furniture and agriculture equipment's.

*Anogessus latifolia (Roxb. Ex DC):*A deciduous tree with grayish, hard, shining and smooth wood in irregular shaped. Sapwood is yellow in young trees and branchless, heartwood very hard. The

wood is highly valued on account of its great strength and touches. It is used for agriculture implementation and in shipping usages.

Azadiracta indica A.Juss. : It is large tree with the bole of 15-18 meters and found in deciduous forest area. Wood hard close grained, sapwood is grayish white. The heartwood is red when first exposed and later turns reddish brown. White ants not attacks on wood.

Diospyrus melanoxylon Roxb. :Middle size deciduous tree reaching height of 50ft. commonly grow in hilly forests. The wood is large reddish brown, with irregular black heartwood. The tree used for furnished good ebony.

Comparative anatomy of root wood

Lagerstroemia lanceolata Wall.ex.w. : It is a large deciduous tree with white, smooth peeling off in thin flask like paper prepared from bark. The sapwood is grayish or with pinkish tinge. The heartwood is light reddish-brown turning to walnut brown on exposé. The wood is mordantly hard and durable even in contact with water. The wood is used for building construction, ships, coffee and furniture's.

Melia azedarach L.: It is moderate size 7-10 meter tall, deciduous tree. The wood is soft sapwood is yellowish white and the heartwood is red. The wood is useful and pretty for museum cassis and furniture and durable.

Prosopis julifera DC: It is small to moderate evergreen tree with dark to light bark in colour. The wood is hard at maturity. Sapwood is large, whitish and the heartwood is reddish brown to black on exposure.

Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.: It is large deciduous tree, wood is very hard close grained giving a red resin. Sapwood is small and the heartwood is yellowish brown with darker stickers. The heartwood is full of gum resin and stains yellow when damp. The wood gum is much used in medicine like diabetes and others.

Zizphus xylopyra (Retz.): It is small deciduous tree, wood is reddish or yellowish brown with a dark colored center and no heartwood, there for this wood is not good as *Z. jujube* but still used for agriculture implements and as firewood.

Comparative anatomy of stem wood

Results of heartwood and sapwood Studies:

Table iv. Comparative vascular anatomy from stem and root

Sr. no.	Plant Name	Vessel per unit area		Parenchyma	
		Stem	Root	Stem	Root
1	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i> (L) Willd.	19-22	8-9	Thick bounded less abundant	Thick bounded abundant
2	<i>Anogessus latifolia</i> (Roxb. Ex DC)	>100	40-50	Paratrachial less abundant	Paratrachial abundant
3.	<i>Azadiracta indica</i> A.Juss.	18-22	6-7	Less abundant	Abundant
4.	<i>Diospyrus melanoxylon</i> Roxb.	25-29	18-20	Apotracheal bounded shows single layerd band less abundant	Abundant
5.	<i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Wall.	53-56	25-28	Aliform confluent to banded less abundant	Aliform confluent to banded abundant
6.	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	22-24	9-10	Less abundant	Abundant
7.	<i>Prosopis julifera</i> DC	20-22	7-8	Less abundant	Abundant
8.	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxb.	21-23	5-6	banded Type less abundant	Abundant
9.	<i>Zizphus xylopyra</i> (Retz.)	78-90	43-47	Scattered apocentric less abundant	Scattered apocentric abundant

The information in regards to heartwood formation in angiosperm is merge in spite of the fact that heartwood is prized for its many values. Plant hormone e play important role in heartwood formation. Auxins, Cytokines, Absecsic acid and ethylene are main groups of plant hormones (Shigo & Hillis 1973). Ethylene is known to play important role in heartwood formation (Nelson and Hillis 1978). I the present investigation the effect of ethylene releasing and inhibiting chemicals on heartwood formation in four angiospermic trees has been recorded which included *Albizia lebbeck*, *Anogessus latifolia*, *Melia azedarach* and *Pterocarpus marsupium*.

There was a production of induced heartwood formation at the site of injury in all the four tree species. Only the degree of radial extensions occurred according to radial extension effected by treatment. Maximum radial extension occurred at 2000 ppm concentration of ACC

(Aminocyclopane carboxylic acid). While in *Azadiracta indica* inhibition of heartwood formation was maximum at 2000 ppm of serine tetroxide chloride (Satish V. Deore 2016).

In *Melia azedarach* the radial extension of induce heartwood was less than in *Azadiracta indica* even at 2000 ppm concentration of ACC. At this concentration there was an increases production of gum in *Melia azedarach*.

Conclusion

It find out the heartwood formation pattern with respect to plant species and its parts some noticeable and conclusive result that the deciduous tree species the radial extension of heartwood is comparatively less than evergreen species. The amount of heartwood is less in gum producing trees except in *Acacia nilotica*, which both the gummosis and well-formed heartwood are present. In general the number of vessels per unit area in root wood is less than that of stem wood while the amount of parenchyma is higher than root wood compared to stem wood.

References

- Abrams MD, Copenheaver CA, Terazawa K, Umeki K, Takiya M, Akashi N (1999) A 370-year dendroecological history of an old-growth Abies-Acer-Quercus forest in Hokkaido, northern Japan. *Can J For Res* 29:1891–1899
- Bisht B.S. and Kothari B. P., (2001). Land cover changes analysis of Garur Ganga Watershed Using GIS/Remote Sensing Technique. *Indian Sco. of Remote Sensing*. Vol. 29 (3): Pp-165-174
- Chilar J., (2000). Land cover mapping of large area from satellite: status and research priorities. *International journal of remote sensing*. Vol. 21 (67): Pp- 1093-1114
- Khan P A (2014). “Tissue culture studies in *Hemidesmus indicus* (L.) R. Br.”. *Golden Research Thought*. ISSN: 2231-5063 Vol:4 (6). PP-1-6, IF: 2.2052 (UIF)
- Nelson and Hillis (1978). Xylem ethylene, phenol-oxidizing enzymes. and nitrogen and heartwood formation in walnut and cherry. *Can. J. Bot.* 56:626-634.
- Pant D. N. and Roy P. S., (1994). Anayazing forest cover and land use dynamic in central Himalayan using remote sensing and GIS. *ISRS Symposium Dheradun India*. Pp- 44-52
- Patil MB and Khan P A (2017a). Ethnobotanical, phytochemical and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven.

Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences. Vol. 10 Issue 2 PP 950-955 (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 21822.)

- Patil MB and Khan P A (2017b)“Primary Phytochemical Studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven for Secondary Metabolites”. Int J Pharm Bio Sci 2017 Apr ; 8(2): (P) 320-323. SJIF 6.268 (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 17357.) IF: 6.268
- Sarma V. V., Murali Krishana G., Hema Malini B. and Nageswara Rao K., (2001). Land use/Land cover changes detection through remote sensing and its climatic implications in the Godavari Delta region. . Jr. Ind. Soc. Rem Sensing. Vol. 29: Pp- 89-91
- Satish V. Deore (2016). Study of Forest Change Detection in Pathri Reserve Forest by Using Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Systems Technologies. International Journal of Science Info (IJSI). Vol. I. Issue 2 PP 52-59
- Shigo, A. L.. And W. E. Hillis. (1973). Heartwood, discolored wood, and micro-organisms in living trees. Ann. Rev. Phytopath. 11: 197-222.

